

From Cherry Orchards to Digital Studios: Cross-Sectoral Partnerships Driving Place-Based Innovation in Rural Portugal

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This presentation examines the Fundão video game cluster case study from the GAME-ER Horizon Europe project [101132585], showcasing how cross-sectoral collaboration transformed a rural Portuguese municipality facing depopulation into an emerging innovation hub. Drawing on primary data collection, including semi-structured interviews, documentary analysis, and participatory mapping exercises, we present insights into the mechanisms through which partnerships between traditional and digital sectors created mutual value and territorial resilience.

Fundão's Innovation Strategy, launched in 2012, deliberately positioned the municipality as an interface connecting traditional sectors—particularly agriculture and textiles—with emerging digital industries. The Living Lab Cova da Beira model facilitated unprecedented collaboration among diverse actors: the University of Beira Interior, local game studios, agricultural producers, technology companies, and civic associations. Rather than replacing existing economic activities, the strategy created synergies. For instance, AgroTech 4.0 initiatives apply digital technologies and innovation to agricultural modernisation, while game development companies benefit from different gamification initiatives in the municipality and partnerships with the university's computer science programmes and access to applied research opportunities in sectors like health, agriculture, and heritage.

Key success factors included the municipality's active mediating role, development of shared infrastructure (coworking spaces and incubators), and collective actions such as joint international showcasing at industry events, mentoring networks, and talent retention programmes. Cross-sectoral partnerships extended beyond economic collaboration to encompass social integration measures—bilingual education, cultural exchange events, and family support services—that welcomed international talent while maintaining connections to local heritage and traditional knowledge.

The Fundão case challenges assumptions about rural-urban dichotomies in creative industries and demonstrates that peripheral regions can cultivate dynamic ecosystems through intentional boundary-spanning partnerships. This presentation will discuss both successes and ongoing challenges, offering practical insights for regions, policymakers and practitioners seeking to foster place-based innovation through multi-sectoral collaboration in non-urban contexts.

Keywords: GAME-ER, Fundão, Rural Innovation Ecosystems, Videogame Clusters, Place-based Development.